

**THE EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEACHING STYLE ON
CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AMONG ENGLISH TEACHERS
IN KAPALONG DISTRICT**

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The Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Style on Classroom Management among English Teachers in Kapalong District

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of emotional intelligence and teaching style to classroom management of English teaching in Kapalong district. The study was quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive-correlational approach. A sample of 60 teachers of the high schools in Kapalong district were identified using complete enumeration sampling answered the surveys on the three variables. Results showed that the level of emotional intelligence, teaching style, and classroom management were all high in level. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and classroom management. Likewise, there was also a significant relationship between teaching style and classroom management of the teachers. Moreover, results showed that domains of emotional intelligence such as self-emotion appraisal and use of emotion can significantly influence classroom management. Finally, it revealed that a domain of teaching style which is teacher-student interaction predict classroom management of the respondents. Results implied that the variables were significant in improving the classroom management of the English teachers. It implies that educational institutions should provide professional development opportunities for English teachers to enhance their emotional intelligence, with a specific focus on emotion regulation. This could include workshops, seminars, or online courses. English teachers should focus on making themselves flexible and adaptable in their teaching style, taking into account students' needs in their decision-making process. They should also focus on engaging in proactive classroom management and discipline strategies, building positive relationships with students, and creating an engaging and inclusive classroom environment.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, teaching styles, classroom management, English teachers, Philippines*

Introduction

In an English class, classroom management can also influence the development of an effective method of teaching and learning. Ineffective classroom management might result in learning activities that are not engaging for the students. It makes the teachers unhappy, stressful, and ultimately prevents them from providing the knowledge that the students need (Jayadi et al., 2022). According to Tahir et al. (2018), the main issues with classroom management among English teachers that impact their performance and the students' learning are the class size, language and cognitive differences, resistance to new methods, lack of audio-visual skills, behavior problems, anxiety, outdated teaching methods, and syllabus implementation.

Classroom management as teacher's problem gain a wide acknowledgment in the county of Indonesia. One of the major challenges encountered by English teachers in a public junior high school located in Semarang Regency, Indonesia, is effectively managing their classrooms, particularly in rural areas. The primary issue they grapple with is the disruptive behavior of students during English lessons. Teachers emphasize that addressing this misbehavior is of utmost importance. It was also mentioned that the teachers' approach to classroom management varies based on the specific needs of their students (Irawati & Listyani, 2020).

In the Philippines, classroom management is a significant issue faced by teachers, particularly in public secondary schools. Classroom management is described as one of the most challenging aspects of teaching, especially for new educators. This indicates a widespread struggle among teachers to maintain effective classroom environments including discipline issues, inadequate preparation, and the need for structured routines. Addressing these problems is essential for improving educational outcomes for students. The findings indicate that classroom discipline is the best predictor of effective classroom management which implies that issues related to maintaining discipline can significantly impact learning outcomes (Sorbetto et al., 2022).

Since this is an important matter that has to be addressed, a study is needed to be conducted. It is important because it is important to understand the current state of teachers' classroom management, teaching style, and emotional intelligence that could affect their effectiveness as teachers. By gathering data on the factors that contribute to teachers' classroom management, educational institutions can make informed decisions and take steps to enhance the quality of education. This can lead to the development of more informed teacher training programs and policies, which in turn can enhance the educational experiences of students in Kapalong district, potentially serving as a model for improvements in other regions. Furthermore, understanding the challenges that teachers face in different contexts can help policymakers and institutions develop targeted interventions to improve teachers' classroom management.

The investigations about the teachers' classroom management have been conducted numerous times, aiming to identify causes and explore potential solutions, given the seriousness of the situation. In connection, there are several research that focus on the problem of the classroom management just like the study of Kanbur et al. (2023) entitled "Interaction between Teachers' Emotional Intelligence and Classroom Management", and the study of Muhammed and Ahmed (2023) entitled "Investigating EFL University Teachers' Classroom Management Competency", which focused on classroom management and emotional intelligence. Furthermore, these

studies have not come across the study in the Philippines specifying the effect of emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management of the English teachers. The necessity that the researcher sees to conduct the study is in order to show the impact that classroom management may have on emotional intelligence and teaching style among the English teachers in Kapalong district schools.

Ultimately, the results will be shared by publishing the research in reputable scholarly journals that focused on emotional intelligence, teaching styles, and classroom management of the English teachers. Moreover, the findings will be showcased in educational conferences on a local and regional level in order to exchange ideas and receive input from colleagues. As a result, the researcher sought to reach a diverse audience of educators and researchers by publishing in a peer-reviewed journal and giving presentations at academic conferences, in order to tackle the discussed problems and put the recommended solutions into practice.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management. To be specific, this study sought answers to the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. self-emotion appraisal;
 - 1.2. others' emotion appraisal;
 - 1.3. use of emotion; and
 - 1.4. regulation of emotion.
2. To determine the level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. teacher-student interaction;
 - 2.2. decision-making negotiation;
 - 2.3. teaching structuring; and
 - 2.4. behavioral control.
3. To determine the level of classroom management of English teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. discipline;
 - 3.2. teaching and learning; and
 - 3.3. personal dimension.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. emotional intelligence and classroom management; and
 - 4.2. teaching style and classroom management.
5. To determine the significant effect of the domains of emotional intelligence and teaching style that can possibly predict classroom management.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Quantitative research is the examination of relationship among variables using sampling techniques and statistical analysis. This type of research relies on numerical data that allows precise measurement, objectivity, and control. Surveys, experiments, or analyzing naturally occurring data are used to obtain the collection and analysis of numerical data. Statistical procedures are used to analyze the numerical data, identify pattern, relationships, and to make predictions about the broader population (Kharbach, 2023).

Thus, this study was quantitative in nature wherein sampling techniques and statistical analysis were used in order to examine the relationship of emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management among English teachers. In the collection of data, survey responses from the English teachers were collected to see if there is significant patterns and relationships between the emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management.

Moreover, descriptive-correlational research involved observing two or more variables in order to determine and establish the extent and the direction of the statistically corresponding relationship. This design produced indexes that show both direction and the strength of the relationship among variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. The survey method is the common method of this approach which involves random sampling of target participants, in which these participants fill a questionnaire centered on the subject matter (Thomas & Zubkov, 2023).

In essence, descriptive-correlational research design was crucial in this study to determine and establish the extent and direction of the relationship of teaching style and classroom management mediated by emotional intelligence among English teacher. Using the design, the researcher gathered large amount of data through survey which the collected data used to test the strength of the relationship between variables. Therefore, this design was appropriate for this study because it allowed the researcher to identify any correlation between variable without manipulating them in any way.

Regression is a statistical technique for examining the relationship between independent and dependent variables. It helps predict the

value of the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variables. The primary objective of regression analysis is to identify the most suitable line or curve that represents the association between the variables. Additionally, through data analysis and regression modeling, researchers can make well-informed decisions, detect trends, and verify hypotheses (Spillane, 2022).

In the context of the study, regression analysis is crucial in this study to predict the value of classroom management based on the values of emotional intelligence and teaching style. By depicting classroom management as a result of these separate factors, the regression analysis enabled researchers to investigate the ways emotional intelligence and teaching approach affect levels of classroom management, emphasizing their influence on the well-being and performance of both English teachers and students. This method emphasized the significance of utilizing regression analysis to understand the intricate relationships among emotional intelligence, teaching style, and classroom management.

Respondents

The respondents of this study involved the junior and senior high school English teachers who are teaching at Kapalong East and West District in the S.Y. 2023-2024. Particularly, these include English teachers coming from different high schools in Kapalong district and must be a graduate from Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is all about the emotional intelligence, teaching style, and the classroom management of the English teachers. Since the study involved the characteristics of a teacher, it was accurate and valid to include all the English teachers from the different high schools in Kapalong district. A total of 60 English teachers across Kapalong District high schools were the respondents of the study. The teachers who were selected as respondents were chosen since the focus of the study was on the effect of independent variables on classroom management among English teachers, making it fitting and valid to include the English teachers in the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School	5	5	8.3%
Doña Carmen Soriano National High School	6	6	10 %
Kamansi Integrated School	4	4	6.7%
Kapalong National High School	17	17	28.3%
Luna National High School	6	6	10%
Mabantao National High School	5	5	8.3%
Ramon Segundo Sr. National High School	5	5	8.3%
Sampao Intergrated School	3	3	5%
Semong National High School	4	4	6.7%
Sua-on National High School	5	5	8.3%
Total	60	60	100%

Complete enumeration is basically used to estimate the unknown parameters of the population. A research method where the entire population under study is included in the research sample. In complete enumeration the information is obtained from every unit of entire population. Complete enumeration is often feasible for smaller populations or when resources allow for data collection from every member of the population. This approach ensures that the sample accurately represents the entire population, as there is no sampling error involved (Gautam, 2020).

The complete enumeration method is particularly appropriate in this study as the respondents of this research was selected based on every individual that belongs to the defined population, which were the English teachers in Kapalong district. To determine the sample, the researcher gather first the data on the population of the respondents by writing a formal letter to each principal of every high school in Kapalong East and West District, requesting access to the target population of respondents. After getting the data, the researcher tabulated the data in the Microsoft Excel and sent the tabulated data to the statistician for the computation of sample.

Instrument

In order to gather the necessary data to address the research questions in the study, the researcher adopted three downloadable questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instrument for emotional intelligence was from the study of Mayer and Salovey (1997) and was adopted by the study of Wong and Law (2002) entitled “The effects of leader and follower emotional intelligence on performance and attitude: An exploratory study”. It yielded a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.79, which indicates that the questionnaire has acceptable internal consistency, and it is, reliable.

Moreover, the instrument for teaching style is from the study of Abello et. al. (2020) entitled” Development and validation of the Teaching Styles Inventory for Higher Education (TSIHE)” which yielded a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.99 which indicates that the questionnaire presents appropriate psychometrical properties to use for research and practical purposes. Also, the instrument for classroom management is from the study of Muring & Venture-Escote (2023) entitled “Classroom Management Techniques and Teaching Performance of Public Elementary Teachers in Montevista, Davao de Oro”. The reliability statistics for this instrument yielded a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.904, which indicates that the questionnaire has an excellent internal consistency, and it is, therefore, highly reliable. These questionnaire was utilized to assess the effect of emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management among English teachers.

This study used a five-point Likert scale as the foundation for measure the level of teaching style, classroom management, and emotional intelligence among English teachers. The questionnaires are measured with 5 items in every indicator in the scale. The Likert scale consisted of five points, ranging from “very high” to “very low”. The values chosen by the respondents for each item were added together to compute their overall score. High scores indicate effective teaching style.

In addition, the content validity of the survey research questionnaires was verified through a validation process. The research committee was provided first the draft of the research instruments for feedback, suggestions, and recommendations on how to improve its presentation, with revisions included and executed. The research panel was then given the final text to examine and revise. The errors, criticisms, and suggestions of the expert validators were included into final edition before data collection. Finally, the result of the validators’ assessments was combined to determine the questionnaire’s status.

Procedure

The following process were used to collect the data:

Questionnaire Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires online which are relevant to the three variables used in the study.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. After the questionnaires were developed, it then submitted to the panel of experts in order to be evaluated and checked. The researcher followed the suggestions and correct the corrections of the panel of experts in revising the questionnaires.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. Through a letter, the researcher sought permission from the Department of Education (DepEd) and from the principals of each institution to conduct the study among the English teachers. These include the junior high school and senior high school English teacher and must be a graduate of the program Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Upon getting consent from the Department of Education (DepEd) and institutions’ principals, the researchers asked each teacher for consent on administering the questionnaire to them. When got consented, the gathering of data starts using paper and pen in answering the questionnaire. After the answering of the questionnaire, the research gave some small gift to the teachers and a gratitude for participating. This resulted in the simple and methodical collection of data.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. The researchers collected data, analyzed it with the assistance of a statistician, and interpreted the findings according to the study’s objectives. The conclusion and recommendation were formulated based on the data from the final dataset.

Data Analysis

The collected information from the survey was counted and analyzed with various statistical methods. The statistical methods employed in analyzing data and testing the hypothesis were at a significance level of alpha 0.05.

Mean. This was utilized to assess the emotional intelligence level, teaching approach, and management of classrooms by English teachers.

Person r Correlation. This was utilized to establish the link between emotional intelligence and classroom management, as well as teaching style and classroom management within English teachers.

Regression. This was utilized to ascertain the significant impact of emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management among English teachers.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were the junior and senior high school English teachers of Kapalong district. To ensure the sound conduct of the study, ethical considerations are addressed and considered accordingly. In this instance, the researcher made sure the respondents’ rights, safety, and reliance on the researcher, as well as the study’s goals, treated with fairness and righteous actions.

Informed Consent. 'Informed' and 'consent' are vital aspects of the term, requiring thorough examination. Participants were fully briefed on the expectations, the planned utilization of the information, and any possible adverse consequences. The participants received explicit, voluntary, and documented consent to join the research, indicating their understanding of their ability to access their data and withdraw whenever they choose. Considering the informed consent procedure as a formal contract between the participants and the researcher (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this case, the researcher included the informed consent question in a printed survey form, ask the target respondents if they are willing to participate and answer the survey form and become part of the study as respondents despite the risks. The respondents were allowed to make voluntary and informed decisions about participating in the study. During the informed consent process, the respondents were oriented about the study, its purpose, procedures, potential risks, benefits, and any other relevant details. They also have the opportunity to withdraw at any time without facing negative consequences. The respondents have the rights to refuse in

participating, refuse on answering sensitive questions, and they have the rights to ask questions about the study. Also, they have the rights to be informed about the results of the study.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. Participant anonymity and participant confidentiality are often mistakenly used interchangeably despite the fact that they have distinct meanings. When a participant remains anonymous, the researcher has no knowledge of their identity. Participant confidentiality means that the researcher knows who the participant is, but keeps their identity confidential and anonymizes the data. The research design carefully addressed both anonymity and confidentiality to minimize risks of harms to participants, researchers, the broader community, and the institution (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018).

In essence, the Data Privacy Act of 2012, strict measure was implemented to safeguard the security and privacy of the gathered data. Names and addresses were meticulously removed to maintain the anonymity and cleanliness of the data. The researcher will safely store all the data throughout the research. Moreover, the researcher established clear procedures in handling and storing the data gathered, and data were destroyed after three years when the study was accomplished or published. Additionally, to avoid potential social harm, the study ensured the security and confidentiality of sensitive data before publishing it. The researcher made sure to safeguard the personal information of participants to deal with this issue. Survey questions did not inquire about personal details like name, email address, or phone number from respondents.

Conflict of Interest. To ensure the ethics approval committee can provide guidance on managing the conflict of interest, it is crucial to openly report any existing connections or past actions by the researcher in an ethics application (Berg & Lune, 2017).

In this study, the researcher addressed conflicts to ensure that the research was conducted ethically, with honesty and fairness, and that the results were credible and unbiased. The researcher was not consciously or unconsciously manipulating data or interpretations to align with personal or financial interests, compromising the objectiveness of the study. Therefore, the researcher emphasized the importance of honesty, integrity, and transparency. Nonetheless, the researcher of the study claimed that no commercial or financial relationships existed that could be interpreted as posing a conflict of interest over the course of the research.

Results and Discussion

Presented in the selection below discusses the emotional intelligence, teaching style, and classroom management data of English teachers in Kapalong district. The chapter discussed data regarding emotional intelligence levels, teaching style levels, classroom management levels, the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching style on classroom management, and the potential predictive effect of emotional intelligence and teaching style domains on classroom management.

Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Self-emotion Appraisal

The level of emotional intelligence of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, self-emotion appraisal. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of self-emotion appraisal. The data revealed that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-emotion appraisal has a total mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicate that the level of emotional intelligence of the English teachers in terms of self-emotion appraisal is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.48 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 - Being aware of whether or not I am happy.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.63 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Expressing my emotions to others easily.

Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Other's Emotion Appraisal

The level of emotional intelligence of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, other's emotion appraisal. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 2. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Self-emotion Appraisal*

	<i>Self-emotion appraisal</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Having good understanding of my own emotions.	4.42	Very High
2.	Being able to express my emotions in a healthy and constructive way.	4.37	Very High
3.	Having a good understanding on the reasons behind my emotional responses.	4.22	High
4.	Being aware of whether or not I am happy.	4.48	Very High
5.	Expressing my emotions to others easily.	3.63	High
	Overall	4.22	High

Presented in Table 3 is the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of other's emotion appraisal. The data revealed that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of other's emotion appraisal has a total mean of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicate that the level of emotional intelligence of the English teachers in terms of other's emotion appraisal is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.53 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 3 – Being sensitive to the feelings and emotions of others.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.82 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Interpreting the emotions of the people I interact with correctly.

Table 3. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Others' Emotion Appraisal*

<i>Others' Emotion Appraisal</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Recognizing my friends' emotions from their behaviour most of the time.	3.85	High
2.	Being a good observer of others' emotions.	4.17	High
3.	Being sensitive to the feelings and emotions of others.	4.53	Very High
4.	Having good understanding of the emotions of people around me.	4.00	High
5.	Interpreting the emotions of the people I interact with correctly.	3.82	High
Overall		4.07	High

Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Use of Emotion

The level of emotional intelligence of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, use of emotion. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed above.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of use of emotion. The data revealed that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of use of emotion I has a total mean of 4.54 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of emotional intelligence of the English teachers in terms of use of emotion appraisal is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.75 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Expressing appropriate emotions in a professional setting.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.28 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 2 – Telling myself I am a competent person most of the time.

Table 4. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Use of Emotion*

<i>Use of Emotion</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Setting goals for myself and then try my best to achieve them.	4.58	Very High
2.	Telling myself I am a competent person most of the time.	4.28	Very High
3.	Being a self-motivated person to achieve my goals and pursue my dreams.	4.55	Very High
4.	Encouraging myself to try my best in handling my emotions in a decision-making process.	4.53	Very High
5.	Expressing appropriate emotions in a professional setting.	4.75	Very High
Overall		4.54	Very High

Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Regulation of Emotion

The level of emotional intelligence of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, regulation of emotion. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 5. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in Terms of Regulation of Emotion*

<i>Regulation of Emotion</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Being able to control my temper and handle difficulties rationally.	4.17	High
2.	Being quite capable of controlling my own emotions in a challenging situation.	4.00	High
3.	Calming down quickly when I am very angry.	3.72	High
4.	Having good control of my own emotions.	3.88	High
5.	Calming down easily when I am feeling anxious or stressed.	3.67	High
Overall		3.89	High

Presented in Table 5 is the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of regulation of emotion. The data revealed that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of regulation of emotion I has a total mean of 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicate that the level of emotional intelligence of the English teachers in terms of regulation of emotion appraisal is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Being able to control my temper and handle difficulties rationally.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.67 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Calming down easily when I am feeling anxious or stressed.

Summary of the Level of Emotional Intelligence

Presented in Table 6 is the overall level of emotional intelligence of English teachers in terms of self-emotion appraisal, others' emotion appraisal, use of emotion, and regulation of emotion.

The data revealed that the level of emotional intelligence of English teachers has a total mean of 4.18 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that emotional intelligence in oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest mean is 4.54 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of use of emotion is always manifested by the respondents.

Table 6. Summary of the Level of Emotional Intelligence

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Self-Emotion Appraisal	4.22	High
Others' Emotion Appraisal	4.07	High
Use of Emotion	4.54	Very High
Regulation of Emotion	3.89	High
Overall	4.18	High

In contrast, the lowest indicator is regulation of emotion which obtain a mean of 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of regulation of emotion is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Additionally, self-emotion appraisal obtained a mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-emotion appraisal is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Lastly, the others' emotion appraisal indicator obtained a mean of 4.07, which also falls within the high range. This indicates that the level of emotional intelligence of the English teachers, with a focus on others' emotion appraisal, was oftentimes manifested and consistently considered to be of high.

Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Teacher-student Interaction

The level of teaching style of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, teacher-student interaction. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of teacher-student interaction. The data revealed that the level of teaching style in terms of teacher-student interaction has a total mean of 4.40 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of teaching style of the English teachers in terms of teacher-student interaction is always manifested.

Table 7. Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Teacher-student Interaction

<i>Teacher-student Interaction</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Acting as a mediator when a conflict exists between students.	4.70	Very High
2.	Allowing my students to approach to share their personal problems.	4.60	Very High
3.	Showing interest in getting to know and bonding with students.	4.42	Very High
4.	Having a close relationship with students.	4.03	High
5.	Greeting the students outside the classroom.	4.27	Very High
Overall		4.40	Very High

The highest mean is 4.70 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Acting as a mediator when a conflict exists between students.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.03 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Having a close relationship with students.

Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Decision-making Negotiation

The level of teaching style of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, decision-making negotiation. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of decision-making negotiation. The data revealed that the level of teaching style in terms of decision-making negotiation has a total mean of 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicate that the level of teaching style of the English teachers in terms of decision-making negotiation is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.67 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Being flexible with the activities proposed in the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS).

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Agreeing with my students' actions to be followed when facing unforeseen situations.

Table 8. *Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Decision-making Negotiation*

<i>Decision-making Negotiation</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Being flexible with the activities proposed in the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS).	4.67	Very High
2.	Preferring to reach agreements rather than imposing decisions.	3.95	High
3.	Setting rules in the classroom like schedule on recess, and use of mobile telephones.	4.60	Very High
4.	Agreeing with my students' actions to be followed when facing unforeseen situations.	3.22	High
5.	Adjusting subject matters to the group's interests and needs.	4.45	Very High
Overall		4.18	High

Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Teaching Structuring

The level of teaching style of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, teaching structuring. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of teaching structuring. The data revealed that the level of teaching style in terms of teaching structuring has a total mean of 4.62 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of teaching style of the English teachers in terms of teaching structuring is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.67 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Providing feedback on students' performance throughout the quarter. In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.58 but with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 2 – Carrying out clearly established routines during the class session and in item no. 3 – Developing the subject following a clear structure.

Table 9. *Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Teaching Structuring*

<i>Teaching Structuring</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Starting the class session by presenting the activities that will be developed.	4.63	Very High
2.	Carrying out clearly established routines during the class session.	4.58	Very High
3.	Developing the subject following a clear structure.	4.58	Very High
4.	Providing feedback on students' performance throughout the quarter.	4.67	Very High
5.	Making the assessments described in the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS).	4.65	Very High
Overall		4.62	Very High

Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Behavioral Control

The level of teaching style of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, behavioral control. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of behavioral control. The data revealed that the level of teaching style in terms of behavioral control has a total mean of 4.58 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of teaching style of the English teachers in terms of behavioral control is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.75 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Ensuring that there is silence when the students are asked to talk/answer during classes. In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.48 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Paying constant attention to all the misbehavior of the students.

Table 10. *Level of Teaching Style in Terms of Behavioral Control*

<i>Behavioral Control</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Paying constant attention to all the misbehavior of the students.	4.48	Very High
2.	Confronting students when they exhibit an inappropriate behavior.	4.55	Very High
3.	Generating corrective actions when I see that one or several students are not paying attention.	4.62	Very High
4.	Ensuring that there is silence when the students are asked to talk/answer during classes.	4.75	Very High
5.	Demanding from my students, appropriate behavior during classes.	4.50	Very High
Overall		4.58	Very High

Summary of the Level of Teaching Style

Presented in Table 11 is the overall level of teaching style of English teachers in terms of teacher-student interaction, decision-making negotiation, teaching structuring, and behavioral control. The data revealed that the level of teaching style of English teachers has a

total mean of 4.45 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that teaching style in always manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest mean is 4.62 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of teaching style in terms of teaching structuring is always manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is decision-making negotiation which obtain a mean of 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teaching style in terms of decision-making negotiation is oftentimes manifested.

Additionally, teacher-student interaction obtained a mean of 4.40 which means very high. This indicates that the level of teaching style in terms of teacher-student interaction is always manifested.

Lastly, the behavioral control indicator obtained a mean of 4.58, which also falls within the very high range. This indicates that the level of teaching style of the English teachers, with a focus on behavioral control, was always manifested and consistently considered to be of very high.

Table 11. *Summary of the Level of Teaching Style*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Teacher-Student Interaction	4.40	Very High
Decision-Making Negotiation	4.18	High
Teaching Structuring	4.62	Very High
Behavioral Control	4.58	Very High
Overall	4.45	Very High

Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Discipline

The level of classroom management of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, discipline. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 12 is the level of classroom management of English teachers in terms of discipline. The data revealed that the level of classroom management in terms of discipline has a total mean of 4.45 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of classroom management of the English teachers in terms of discipline is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.82 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 3 – Making students aware of the consequences for misbehavior (e.g., loss of breaktime, extra classroom time).

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Redirecting inappropriate behavior on the spot.

Table 12. *Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Discipline*

<i>Discipline</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Involving students in establishing rules and procedures.	4.43	Very High
2. Sharing with students the reasons behind the disciplinary approach(es) I use.	4.77	Very High
3. Making students aware of the consequences for misbehavior (e.g., loss of breaktime, extra classroom time).	4.83	Very High
4. Using class time to reflect on appropriate behavior with students as a group.	4.20	High
5. Redirecting inappropriate behavior on the spot.	4.00	High
Overall	4.45	Very High

Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Teaching and Learning

The level of classroom management of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, teaching and learning. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of classroom management of English teachers in terms of teaching and learning. The data revealed that the level of classroom management in terms of teaching and learning has a total mean of 4.57 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of classroom management of the English teachers in terms of teaching and learning is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.77 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 2 – Making sure that the learning objectives are clearly stated for students to understand them.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.15 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Finishing the class with a reflection activity about the lesson (e.g., written reflection, oral reflection, report on what was learnt).

Table 13. *Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Teaching and Learning*

<i>Teaching and Learning</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Taking into account students' previous knowledge to plan the activities based on their level.	4.73	Very High
2.	Making sure that the learning objectives are clearly stated for students to understand them.	4.77	Very High
3.	Organizing the activities into logical stages to fulfil the objectives of the lesson.	4.57	Very High
4.	Giving students instructions on how to report their completed work.	4.63	Very High
5.	Finishing the class with a reflection activity about the lesson (e.g., written reflection, oral reflection, report on what was learnt).	4.15	High
Overall		4.57	Very High

Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Personal Dimension

The level of classroom management of English teachers was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, personal dimension. The response of English teachers on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 14 is the level of classroom management of English teachers in terms of personal dimension. The data revealed that the level of classroom management in terms of personal dimension has a total mean of 4.64 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicate that the level of classroom management of the English teachers in terms of personal dimension is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.87 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Encouraging students to be respectful to one another. In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Attempting to be “Me” rather than “the Teacher” to make students feel I am approachable.

Table 14. *Level of Classroom Management in Terms of Personal Dimension*

<i>Personal Dimension</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Attempting to be “Me” rather than “the Teacher” to make students feel I am approachable.	4.18	High
2.	Using eye contact to make students feel I care about what they say and do.	4.65	Very High
3.	Praising individual accomplishments and important events in students' lives.	4.68	Very High
4.	Encouraging students to be respectful to one another.	4.87	Very High
5.	Helping students to develop their ability to make decisions by themselves.	4.83	Very High
Overall		4.64	Very High

Summary of the Level of Classroom Management

Presented in Table 15 is the overall level of classroom management of English teachers in terms of discipline, teaching and learning, and personal dimension. The data revealed that the level of classroom management of English teachers has a total mean of 4.55 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that classroom management in always manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Table 15. *Summary of the Level of Classroom Management*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Discipline	4.45	Very High
Teaching and Learning	4.57	Very High
Personal Dimension	4.64	Very High
Overall	4.55	Very High

Further, the highest mean is 4.64 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of classroom management in terms of personal dimension is always manifested. In contrast, the lowest indicator is discipline which obtain a mean of 4.45 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of classroom management in terms of discipline is always manifested.

Lastly, the teaching and learning indicator garnered a mean score of 4.57, which also falls within the very high range. This indicates that the level of classroom management, with a focus on teaching and learning, was always observed and consistently considered to be of very high.

Significant Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Classroom Management

Presented in Table 16 is the result of the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and classroom management of the English teachers. The results showed that emotional intelligence garnered a mean of 4.18 and classroom management obtained a mean of 4.55, resulted to have the r-value of $r(114) = 0.419, p < .001$. The r value typically implies the correlation coefficient r being report-

ed along with the degrees of freedom associated with the correlation. In this case, there are two parameters to estimate, therefore degrees of freedom (df) was $n-2$, where n is the sample size. Specifically, the correlation coefficient $r=0.419$ signifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the emotional intelligence and classroom management, indicating that approximately 41.9% of the variability in one variable can be explained by the variability in the other. The remaining percentage (58.1%) represents unexplained variability, possibly stemming from factors not considered in the analysis or random variation.

Since the probability value ($p<.001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between emotional intelligence and classroom management.

Table 16. Significant Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Classroom Management

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Emotional Intelligence	4.18			
Classroom Management	4.55	.419	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Teaching Style and Classroom Management

Presented in Table 17 is the result of the significant relationship between teaching style and classroom management of the English teachers. The results showed that teaching style garnered a mean of 4.45 and classroom management obtained a mean of 4.55, resulted to have the r-value of $r(114) = 0.638, p<.001$. The r value typically implies the correlation coefficient r being reported along with the degrees of freedom associated with the correlation. In this case, there are two parameters to estimate, therefore degrees of freedom (df) was $n-2$, where n is the sample size. Specifically, the correlation coefficient $r=0.638$ signifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the teaching style and classroom management, indicating that approximately 63.8% of the variability in one variable can be explained by the variability in the other. The remaining percentage (36.2%) represents unexplained variability, possibly stemming from factors not considered in the analysis or random variation.

Since the probability value ($p<.001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between teaching style and classroom management.

Table 17. Significant Relationship Between Teaching Style and Classroom Management

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Teaching Style	4.45			
Classroom Management	4.55	.638	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Effect Between Emotional Intelligence and Classroom Management

Presented in Table 18 is the significant effect of the domains or indicators of emotional intelligence towards the level of classroom management among English teachers in Kapalong district. The results showed that two domains of emotional intelligence, self-emotion appraisal and use of emotion, appear to be statistically significant predictors of the classroom management of English teachers – self-emotion appraisal ($\beta=0.213, p<.001$) and use of emotion ($\beta=0.211, p<.05$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is not accepted.

The beta value, $\beta=0.213$, indicates that for every unit increase of self-emotion appraisal, the level of classroom management among English teachers will also increase by 0.213 units. Likewise, the beta value, $\beta=0.211$, indicates that for every unit of use of emotion, the level of classroom management of English teachers will also increase by 0.211 units. Therefore, self-emotion appraisal and use of emotion are the only indicator of emotional intelligence that can significantly influence the classroom management of English teachers.

Table 18. Significant Effect Between Emotional Intelligence and Classroom Management

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.553	0.038			
Self-Emotion Appraisal	0.213	0.07	0.329	<.001	Ho Rejected
Others' Emotion Appraisal	-0.003	0.09	-0.004	.97	Ho Accepted
Use Of Emotion	0.211	0.107	0.296	.05	Ho Rejected
Regulation Of Emotion	0.164	0.104	0.227	.12	Ho Accepted

Dependent Variable: Classroom Management

Note: $R=0.665, R^2=0.442, F\text{-ratio}=10.880, P\text{-value}<.001$

On the other hand, the other two domains – others' emotion appraisal ($\beta=-0.003, p<.97$) and regulation of emotion ($\beta=0.164, p<.12$) – do not have a significant effect on classroom management. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the two domains exceeded

0.05. This suggests that the two domains were not significant predictor of classroom management.

Moreover, teaching style explained a significant proportion of variance in classroom management, $R^2=0.442$, $F\text{-ratio}= 10.880$, $p<.001$. The R^2 of 0.442 shows that the model predicts 44.2% of the statistical variation observed in the level of classroom management among respondents. The coefficient of alienation which is 55.8% points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of classroom management among English teachers in Kapalong district.

Significant Effect of Teaching Style and Classroom Management

Presented in Table 19 is the significant effect of the domains or indicators of emotional intelligence towards the level of classroom management among English teachers in Kapalong district. The result showed that one domain of teaching style which is teacher-student interaction appear to be statistically significant predictors of the classroom management of English teachers – teacher-student interaction ($\beta=0.282$, $p<.002$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The beta value, $\beta=0.282$, indicates that for every unit increase of teacher-student interaction, the level of classroom management among English teachers will also increase by 0.282 units. Therefore, teacher-student interaction is the only indicator of teaching style that can significantly influence the classroom management of English teachers.

Table 19. Significant Effect Between Teaching Style and Classroom Management

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @ =0.05
	Beta	Std. Error			
(Constant)	4.553	0.038		< .001	
Teacher-Student Interaction	0.282	0.086	0.484	.002	Ho Rejected
Decision-Making Negotiation	-0.004	0.086	-0.006	.967	Ho Accepted
Teaching Structuring	0.006	0.096	0.009	.95	Ho Accepted
Behavioral Control	0.042	0.078	0.072	.593	Ho Accepted

Dependent Variable: Classroom Management
 Note: $R= 0.509$, $R^2=0.259$, $F\text{-ratio}= 4.799$ $P\text{-value}= < .002$

On the other hand, the other three domains, decision-making negotiation ($\beta=0.004$, $p<.967$), teaching structuring ($\beta=0.006$, $p<.95$), and behavioral control ($\beta=0.042$, $p<.593$) do not have a significant effect on classroom management. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the two domains exceeded 0.05. This suggests that the three domains were not significant predictor of classroom management.

Moreover, teaching style explained a significant proportion of variance in classroom management, $R^2=0.259$, $F\text{-ratio}= 4.799$, $p<.002$. The R^2 of 0.259 shows that the model predicts 22.9% of the statistical variation observed in the level of classroom management among respondents. The coefficient of alienation which is 77.1% points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of classroom management among English teachers in Kapalong district.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of emotional intelligence, indicating that this variable is oftentimes observed by teachers.

Based on the result of emotional intelligence as perceived by teachers, it was determined to be high. This means that the teacher often observed the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the result of the teaching style of the teachers, it can be also drawn that the level of teaching style among English teachers was very high. This means that the students always manifest the variable. In addition, the teachers were assessed in the preparedness level of classroom management, and it was determined as very high. This means that the classroom management of the English teachers are always manifested.

Furthermore, the correlation between the emotional intelligence and classroom management revealed a significant relationship. The study shows that emotional intelligence has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with classroom management among English teachers. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

In addition, the correlation between teaching style and classroom management also revealed a significant relationship. The study shows that teaching style has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with classroom management among English teachers. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, emotional intelligence two domains have shown significant influence to the classroom management. This means that the domains- self-emotion appraisal and use of emotion- are significantly predictors of classroom management of English teachers. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 44.2% of the statistical variation with an $F= 10.880$ and $p<.001$ in the level of classroom management of the teachers, while the remaining 55.8% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the classroom management of the respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of teaching style has one domain that significantly influence the classroom management of the respondents. This means that the domain- teacher-student interaction- are significantly a predictor of classroom management. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 25.9% of the statistical variation with values of $F= 4.799$ and $p<.002$ in the level of classroom management of the respondents, while the remaining 74.1% refers to other variable that have not been included in the study that may also affect the classroom management of the respondents.

Based on the previously mentioned findings from the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the emotional intelligence indicators, it was found that regulation of emotion has the lowest mean. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that the educational institutions provide professional development opportunities for English teachers to enhance their emotional intelligence, with a specific focus on emotion regulation. This could include workshops, seminars, or online courses. Additionally, incorporating emotional intelligence training into pre-service teacher education programs to ensure that new teachers are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to regulate their emotions effectively. Also, there is a need to provide English teachers with resources and strategies to help them manage their emotions, such as mindfulness practices, stress management techniques, and cognitive restructuring. Teacher could seek feedback from their peers and supervisors regarding their emotional intelligence and classroom management skills, and to use this feedback to identify areas for improvement. By implementing these recommendations, English teachers can improve their emotional intelligence and classroom management skills, leading to a more positive and effective learning environment for students.

Based on the results, decision-making negotiation has been identifies as having the lowest mean among the teaching style indicators. Consequently, a set of targeted recommendations was formulated to improve and strengthen this specific aspect. Several targeted recommendations were proposed to address and enhance this aspect.

Therefore, it is hereby recommended that teachers may focus on making themselves flexible and adaptable in their teaching style, taking into account the environment, students, and the students' needs in their decision-making process. This can be achieved through engaging the students in the decision-making process by including them in the formulation of rules, through creating differentiated activities or adjusting activities that will certainly suits to the interest and needs of the students, and through being firm and just of their decisions and not to be influenced by the students' actions. Furthermore, incorporating self-assessment and reflections on the decision making that have happened inside the classroom can bring a teachers' set of goals of what is truly their authority as a teacher. By knowing how their decision-making process affects their way of teaching and managing the classroom, it can create a more positive and inclusive learning environment.

The findings also revealed that discipline resulted in the lowest mean among classroom management indicators. The findings emphasize the need for improvement in the discipline of the teachers. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that teachers should prioritize proactive classroom management and discipline techniques, like setting clear rules, forming positive connections with students, and fostering an inclusive classroom atmosphere. This might include employing tactics to establish and maintain a structured learning atmosphere, enhance significant academic learning and promote social-emotional development, and boost student academic participation while reducing negative classroom conduct. Moreover, effectively conveying and instructing students on classroom rules and procedures can aid in creating a structured and supportive learning atmosphere. By following these suggestions, educators can enhance classroom management, establish a favorable learning atmosphere, and foster the academic and social-emotional development of every student.

Moreover, for the benefits of future researchers, a recommendation was made to consider employing a mixed-method approach when delving into the intricate interplay between emotional intelligence, teaching style, and classroom management. Although the present study centered on a quantitative research design involving 60 teachers, the utilization of mixed-method approach holds promise for multiple reasons. By integrating both quantitative and qualitative data, researchers can gain a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the complexities involved in these areas, and contribute to the development of more effective teaching strategies and classroom management practices.

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